

Preliminary survey findings on PharmaBot – a retrieval-augmented chatbot for insulin safety information and pharmacovigilance support

Veselina Ruseva¹, Stanimir Dobrev¹, Violeta Getova-Kolarova¹,
Maria Dimitrova¹

¹ Department “Organisation and Economics of pharmacy”, Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University-Sofia, 2 Dunav str., 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Violeta Getova-Kolarova (v.getova@pharmfac.mu-sofia.bg)

Received 23 March 2026 ♦ Accepted 1 April 2026 ♦ Published 15 April 2026

Citation: Ruseva V, Dobrev S, Getova-Kolarova V, Peneva A, Getov I, Dimitrova M, Petkova V (2026) Preliminary survey findings on PharmaBot – a retrieval-augmented chatbot for insulin safety information and pharmacovigilance support. *Pharmacia* 73: 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e192726>

Abstract

Adverse drug reactions (ADRs) pose a significant patient-safety concern, contributing to substantial morbidity, mortality, and healthcare utilization. Source-grounded chatbots have the potential to enhance pharmacovigilance by improving access to regulated medicine information and reducing barriers to ADR reporting. We created a prototype of a web-based chatbot (PharmaBot) designed using retrieval-augmented generation methods to provide responses grounded in summaries of product characteristics and package leaflets. Subsequently, we conducted a cross-sectional survey among 37 participants who were treated with insulin to assess their digital literacy, perceived usefulness, trust, and intended use of the chatbot for drug safety information. The results indicated that most respondents (70.3%) demonstrated high to very high smartphone app skills. Moreover, 73.0% rated the chatbot as useful or very useful, and 78.4% expressed moderate to very high levels of trust in it. About 56.8% of participants reported an intention to use the chatbot regularly (frequently or very frequently). The most popular intended use cases were therapy reminders (81.1%) and information about insulin and therapy (70.3%), while 51.4% chose guidance on ADR reporting. These preliminary findings suggest that users have an acceptable perception of a source-grounded chatbot as a supportive tool for pharmacovigilance-related workflows.

Keywords

adverse drug reaction reporting, artificial intelligence, chatbot, insulin, retrieval-augmented generation

Introduction

Adverse drug reactions (ADRs) are a major patient-safety concern and contribute substantially to morbidity, mortality, and healthcare utilization. (Lazarou et al. 1998) synthesized prospective evidence on serious and fatal ADRs in hospitalized patients, and (Pirmohamed et al. 2004) demonstrated a substantial burden of ADR-related hospital admissions and associated costs in a large prospective analysis.

Despite established regulatory frameworks, pharmacovigilance remains constrained by spontaneous under-reporting. (Hazell and Shakir 2006) reviewed estimates of under-reporting across settings and concluded that under-reporting is substantial, with implications for delayed signal detection and incomplete risk characterization.

Patient-facing digital tools may reduce barriers to accessing reliable safety-related information on medicines and engaging with pharmacovigilance actions.

However, trust and perceived credibility are critical in medicine-safety contexts, particularly because large language models can generate plausible but incorrect text when not appropriately constrained (Bender et al. 2021).

Retrieval-augmented generation combines semantic retrieval from a curated corpus with constrained generation to enhance factual accuracy and traceability (Lewis et al. 2020). In the European Union, regulated product information offers officially approved details for healthcare professionals and patients, including the summary of product characteristics, package leaflet, and labeling (European Medicines Agency n.d.). Grounding chatbot responses in these sources aligns conceptually with pharmacovigilance requirements for accuracy and provenance.

The goal of the current study is to assess the digital literacy, perceived usefulness, trust, and intended use of a web-based retrieval-augmented chatbot designed to provide insulin-related safety information grounded in regulated product documents and to support pharmacovigilance-oriented user needs.

Materials and methods

Study design, participants, and recruitment process

We conducted a cross-sectional questionnaire study to assess user perceptions of PharmaBot among 37 patients with diabetes who are receiving insulin treatment. The inclusion criteria focused on patients undergoing insulin therapy. Participants were recruited over a 1-month pilot period through online distribution and outreach within the patient community, and no incentives were offered.

System description

PharmaBot is a web-based, AI-driven chatbot designed to provide accurate and accessible information on insulin medicines while strengthening pharmacovigilance practices. Its main objective is to improve drug safety awareness and encourage the reporting of adverse drug reactions (ADRs) among both patients and healthcare professionals. By offering reliable, easy-to-understand guidance, the system helps users better understand insulin therapy, recognize potential side effects, and take appropriate reporting actions when safety concerns arise.

The chatbot is built on a retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) framework, which ensures that all responses are grounded in verified medical knowledge. In this approach, the system first retrieves relevant information from a curated corpus of trusted sources, such as clinical guidelines, regulatory documents, and pharmacovigilance databases (Lewis et al. 2020). It then generates responses strictly based on this retrieved content, reducing the risk of misinformation and increasing transparency and reliability. This design allows PharmaBot to deliver context-aware, evidence-based answers tailored to user queries.

Validated information sources

The intended knowledge sources are regulated product-information documents (SmPC and package leaflets). In the EU, product information includes SmPC, package leaflet, and labeling, and is positioned as officially approved information for healthcare professionals and patients (European Medicines Agency n.d.).

Survey instrument

The questionnaire consisted of 15 items that covered the following areas: demographics (age group, education level, residence), diabetes history (years since diagnosis), access to healthcare and pharmacy services, type of therapy, and home glucose-monitoring practices. Digital competence and readiness to use digital tools among the participants were measured using the following metrics on a Likert scale: digital literacy (rated from 1 to 5), perceived usefulness (rated from 1 to 5), trust (rated from 1 to 5), intended frequency of use (rated from 1 to 5), and experiences and attitudes related to the reporting of adverse drug reactions (ADRs, multiple-selection answers).

Ethics and data protection

Participation in the study was voluntary and anonymous, and no personally identifiable information was collected. Data were processed and analyzed in aggregated form only, ensuring participant confidentiality. The study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki (World Medical Association 2013).

Statistical analysis

Descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages) were calculated for categorical variables. For multiple-selection items, percentages may sum to > 100% because respondents could select more than one option. Percentages are reported to one decimal place. To determine the impact of various factors on the frequency of AI chatbot use and trust in the AI chatbot, we performed a multiple linear regression analysis.

Results

Participant characteristics

Participants ($n = 37$) spanned multiple adult age categories, with only a small number of minors (< 18 years) included. Education levels ranged from primary to higher education, with 43% having higher education. Most respondents (43.2%) live in large cities.

Insulin pens were the most frequently reported therapy type (56.8%), with additional use of insulin pumps and hybrid systems (Table 1).

Table 1. Demographic and clinical characteristics of insulin-treated participants.

Characteristic	Category	n (%)
Age group	<18 years	2 (5.4)
	18–25 years	4 (10.8)
	26–35 years	5 (13.5)
	36–45 years	6 (16.2)
	46–55 years	14 (37.8)
	>55 years	6 (16.2)
Higher education	Primary	7 (18.9)
	Secondary	14 (37.8)
	Higher	16 (43.2)
Years living with diabetes	<1 year	11 (29.7)
	1–5 years	7 (18.9)
	6–10 years	9 (24.3)
	>10 years	10 (27.0)
Residence	Village/rural	7 (18.9)
	Small town	10 (27.0)
	Large city (>100,000)	20 (54.1)
Access to a pharmacy or healthcare facility nearby	Yes	29 (78.4)
	No	8 (21.6)
Insulin therapy type	Insulin pens	21 (56.8)
	Hybrid system (pump + sensor with automation)	10 (27.0)
	Insulin pump	5 (13.5)
	Other	1 (2.7)
Home glucose monitoring device use	Yes	33 (89.2)
	No	4 (10.8)

Chatbot acceptability outcomes

Digital readiness and acceptance were generally positive among most respondents, as illustrated in Fig. 1.

A significant 70.3% of respondents reported high to very high smartphone app skills, with scores ranging from 4 to 5. Additionally, 73.0% rated the app as useful or very useful, with scores also between 4 and 5. The regression results show a statistically significant moderate negative relationship between age and usefulness of the AI-based chatbot ($\beta = -0.165, p = 0.004$), with the model explaining about 21% of the variation in the dependent variable.

Trust in the app was moderate to very high for 78.4% of users, who scored their trust levels between 3 and 5.

Figure 1. Distribution of digital literacy, perceived usefulness, trust, and intended frequency of use of PharmaBot ($n = 37$).

However, the regression indicates a weak negative relationship between age and trust ($\beta = -0.107$) that is marginally insignificant ($p \approx 0.051$), explaining about 10% of the variation in the dependent variable.

Furthermore, 56.8% indicated an intention to use the app regularly, scoring their frequency of use as frequent or very frequent (4 to 5).

Overall, the results demonstrate a consistent pattern of positive user perception regarding usability, trust, and adoption intention, although there are variations in statistical significance among the different variables. This pattern suggests that both usability and trust-related factors may support the adoption of source-grounded AI tools in real-world healthcare settings.

Intended use cases and pharmacovigilance linkage

The distribution of intended use cases is presented in Fig. 2. The results indicate that respondents primarily associate the chatbot with daily therapy support functionalities, with therapy reminders (81.1%) and insulin-related information (70.3%) being the most frequently selected options.

As illustrated in Fig. 2, pharmacovigilance-related functionalities were also prominently represented. More than half of respondents selected adverse drug reaction (ADR) information (59.5%) and guidance on where and how to report suspected ADRs (51.4%), suggesting a meaningful alignment between the system's design and pharmacovigilance-related user needs.

Additionally, features supporting clinical communication, such as preparing questions for the clinician (51.4%), were commonly selected, indicating that users perceive the chatbot as a supportive tool in the broader healthcare interaction process.

In contrast, a smaller proportion of respondents (18.9%) indicated that they would not use a chatbot, highlighting the presence of a subgroup with lower acceptance. Overall, Fig. 2 demonstrates that while therapy-related functions dominate, pharmacovigilance features represent a significant and relevant component of user interest.

ADR-related experience and behavior

Ten respondents (27.0%) reported having experienced a suspected adverse drug reaction or medicine-related problem, while 23 (62.2%) reported no such experience, and 4 (10.8%) were unsure.

Among respondents reporting an ADR or medicine-related problem ($n = 10$), the most common actions included consulting a physician (40.0%), reporting through an official channel (40.0%), and seeking advice from a pharmacist (20.0%). These findings indicate that while formal reporting pathways are utilized by a subset of patients, healthcare professionals remain a primary point of contact.

Attitudinal responses revealed variability in awareness and behavioral intention regarding ADR reporting. Notably, a proportion of respondents (32.4%) indicated limited awareness of reporting possibilities or unwillingness to use a chatbot for such purposes.

This highlights the need for targeted trust-building strategies and the integration of educational components within chatbot design to support pharmacovigilance engagement and patient empowerment.

Discussion

This manuscript reports preliminary survey findings on a pharmacovigilance-oriented chatbot grounded in regulated product information. The clinical rationale is supported by evidence that ADRs contribute substantially to serious outcomes and hospital admissions (Lazarou et al. 1998; Pirmohamed et al. 2004) and that under-reporting limits pharmacovigilance sensitivity (Hazell and Shakir 2006).

Our study aimed to evaluate the perception of a retrieval-augmented chatbot (PharmaBot) as a useful and trustworthy tool for pharmacovigilance among insulin-treated patients. We assessed user digital readiness, perceived usefulness, trust, and intended use while examining whether pharmacovigilance functionalities (such as ADR information) met patient needs. The results show initial validation of acceptability, with most participants reporting high digital literacy, positive usefulness ratings, and moderate-to-high trust, while over half intended to use it regularly. Users meaningfully selected pharmacovigilance-related functionalities, indicating that the system aligns with patient expectations. Overall, the findings support the feasibility of such tools in patient-facing pharmacovigilance

Figure 2. Intended use cases of PharmaBot among insulin-treated participants (multiple responses allowed).

contexts and support already published articles on the usefulness of digital technologies in the fields of adherence to therapy (Georgieva et al. 2023) and disease-management control (Nikolov and Petrova 2025).

Our findings suggest that source-grounded AI systems and digital tools can represent a feasible and acceptable approach for supporting patient-facing pharmacovigilance activities. Importantly, the alignment between the intended system functionalities and user-selected use cases—particularly regarding adverse drug reaction (ADR) information and reporting guidance—indicates that such tools address relevant and unmet needs in real-world patient contexts. The combination of daily therapy support (e.g., reminders and treatment-related information) with pharmacovigilance-oriented functionalities may represent a practical and scalable pathway for adoption and sustained engagement. These findings are in line with already published ones supporting the utilization of AI-based tools to support pharmacovigilance and ADR reporting practices (Algarvio et al. 2025).

From a system perspective, grounding responses in EU-regulated product information (SmPC and package leaflets) aligns with the role of product information as an officially approved and scientifically validated source for patients and healthcare professionals (European Medicines Agency n.d.). However, large language models can still produce misleading outputs without appropriate constraints and governance, motivating the use of retrieval augmentation and careful safety design (Bender et al. 2021; Lewis et al. 2020).

Acceptability signals were broadly positive: most respondents reported high digital literacy and rated usefulness and trust favorably, with over half indicating likely regular use. This is consistent with evidence that mobile health engagement is common but socially patterned and that adoption varies with education and literacy-related factors (Ernsting et al. 2017; Graetz et al. 2016).

Trust remains a central barrier in medical AI, and prior work suggests consumers can resist AI-mediated healthcare even when performance is adequate (Longoni et al. 2019). Therefore, the observed subgroup with low or no trust or non-use intention should be interpreted as an

essential design target rather than an outlier. By leveraging validated product information, such systems have the potential to enhance patient awareness, facilitate earlier recognition of ADRs, and lower barriers to reporting, thereby complementing existing pharmacovigilance frameworks.

The strongest “chatbot–survey” linkage is in intended use: pharmacovigilance-relevant tasks (ADR information and reporting guidance) were selected by around half or more of respondents, while therapy support (reminders; insulin information) dominated. This indicates that a combined value proposition—daily self-management support plus safety and reporting navigation—may be a pragmatic adoption pathway.

The findings should be interpreted within the context of a preliminary, exploratory evaluation. The sample size ($n = 37$) is modest and reflects an initial pilot phase, aimed at generating early insights into user perceptions, which could also be considered a limitation of the study. The study design relies on self-reported measures, which capture perceived usability and acceptance rather than observed behavioral outcomes. In addition, the evaluation does not directly assess clinical or pharmacovigilance endpoints. Although the present findings are derived from a pilot sample and should be interpreted within this context, they provide a consistent and interpretable signal regarding user acceptance and perceived value.

A key insight of PharmaBot is its dual role in both education and safety monitoring. Beyond providing general information about insulin use, such as dosage, administration, storage, and interactions, the chatbot actively supports pharmacovigilance by helping users identify possible ADRs and guiding them through the reporting process. It simplifies complex medical information, making it more accessible, and directs users to appropriate national or institutional reporting systems. In doing so, it addresses the common issue of underreporting in drug safety surveillance. Another important aspect is its user-centered communication. PharmaBot adapts its language depending on the user, offering clear, non-technical explanations for patients while still being informative for healthcare professionals. At the same time, it maintains a strong safety framework by avoiding unsupported claims and encouraging consultation with medical experts when necessary.

Nevertheless, the results provide valuable initial evidence regarding the acceptability and perceived relevance of a pharmacovigilance-oriented chatbot grounded in regulated information sources. These findings support the feasibility of the approach and inform the design of subsequent studies. Future research should extend this work through larger and more diverse samples, task-based usability testing, controlled assessments of response accuracy against source documents, and post-deployment monitoring aligned with data protection by design and by default principles (European Commission n.d.; Regulation (EU) 2016/679).

Conclusion

PharmaBot exemplifies a practical application of artificial intelligence in healthcare by integrating trustworthy

information retrieval with natural language interaction. Its key contributions include improving access to reliable information about insulin, supporting the early detection and reporting of adverse reactions, and ultimately fostering safer and more informed medication use. Overall, PharmaBot represents a promising digital health solution with the potential to bridge gaps between patients and pharmacovigilance systems, leading to more accessible, responsive, and patient-centered medication safety practices.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors’ representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

Funding

This study is financed by the European Union–NextGenerationEU through the National Recovery and Resilience Plan of the Republic of Bulgaria, project BG-RRP-2.004-0004-C01 “Strategic research and innovation program for development of Medical University – Sofia.”

Author contributions

All authors participated in the conduct of the study and preparation of the current manuscript, as follows: Conceptualization: VR, MD; Methodology: VR, IG, MD, VG-K; Writing – original draft preparation: VR, MD; Writing – review and editing: MD, IG, VG-K, SD, AP, VP; Visualization: VR; Supervision: IG, MD, VP; Funding acquisition: MD, VP, IG, VG-K.

Author ORCIDs

Violeta Getova-Kolarova <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7103-3892>

Ilko Getov <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6513-9327>

Maria Dimitrova <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4868-7775>

Valentina Petkova <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6938-1054>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

References

- Algarvio RC, Conceição J, Rodrigues PP, Ribeiro I, Ferreira-da-Silva R (2025) Artificial intelligence in pharmacovigilance: a narrative review and practical experience with an expert-defined Bayesian network tool. *International Journal of Clinical Pharmacy* 47(4): 932–944. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11096-025-01975-3>
- Bender EM, Gebru T, McMillan-Major A, Shmitchell S (2021) On the dangers of stochastic parrots: can language models be too big? *Proceedings of the 2021 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability and Transparency*, 610–623. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3442188.3445922>
- Ernsting C, Dombrowski SU, Oedekoven M, O'Sullivan JL, Kanzler M, Kuhlmeier A, Gellert P (2017) Using smartphones and health apps to change and manage health behaviors: a population-based survey. *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 19(4): e101. <https://doi.org/10.2196/jmir.6838>
- European Commission (n.d.) What does data protection “by design” and “by default” mean? European Commission, Brussels.
- European Data Protection Board (2020) Guidelines 4/2019 on Article 25 data protection by design and by default (final version). European Data Protection Board, Brussels. <https://doi.org/10.21552/edpl/2020/4/14>
- European Medicines Agency (n.d.) Product information. European Medicines Agency, Amsterdam. <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/human-regulatory/overview/product-information> [accessed 2026]
- European Medicines Agency (n.d.) Electronic product information for human medicines in the EU: key principles. European Medicines Agency, Amsterdam. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781800885240.ema>
- Georgieva N, Tenev V, Kamusheva M, Petrova G (2023) Diabetes mellitus—digital solutions to improve medication adherence: Scoping review. *Diabetology* 4: 465–480. <https://doi.org/10.3390/diabetology4040040>
- Graetz I, Gordon N, Fung V, Hamity C, Reed ME (2016) The digital divide and patient portals: internet access explained differences in patient portal use for secure messaging by age, race, and income. *Medical Care* 54(8): 772–779. <https://doi.org/10.1097/MLR.0000000000000560>
- Hazell L, Shakir SAW (2006) Under-reporting of adverse drug reactions: a systematic review. *Drug Safety* 29(5): 385–396. <https://doi.org/10.2165/00002018-200629050-00003>
- Lazarou J, Pomeranz BH, Corey PN (1998) Incidence of adverse drug reactions in hospitalized patients: a meta-analysis of prospective studies. *Journal of the American Medical Association* 279(15): 1200–1205. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.279.15.1200>
- Lewis P, Perez E, Piktus A, Petroni F, Karpukhin V, Goyal N, Küttler H, Lewis M, Yih W, Rocktäschel T, Riedel S, Kiela D (2020) Retrieval-augmented generation for knowledge-intensive NLP tasks. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* 33: 9459–9474. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2005.11401>
- Longoni C, Bonezzi A, Morewedge CK (2019) Resistance to medical artificial intelligence. *Journal of Consumer Research* 46(4): 629–650. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jcr/ucz013>
- Nikolov P, Petrova G (2025) Technological and digital innovations in improving adherence to asthma medication therapy. *Pharmacia* 72: 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.72.e148243>
- Pirmohamed M, James S, Meakin S, Green C, Scott AK, Walley TJ, Farrar K, Park BK, Breckenridge AM (2004) Adverse drug reactions as cause of admission to hospital: prospective analysis of 18 820 patients. *BMJ* 329(7456): 15–19. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.329.7456.15>
- Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council (2016) Official Journal of the European Union L 119: 1–88
- World Medical Association (2013) World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki: ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects. *Journal of the American Medical Association* 310(20): 2191–2194. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2013.281053>